

"Spoken Portrait" - Head Description

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ABSTRACT: The description of the signs referred to in the Specialty literature and the "Spoken Portrait" Method, has the characteristics of the body in its entirety, the emphasis being placed on the anatomic features of the face, being covered in the description of the volume, shape, position and color of the observed parts, each element being appreciated in the report with other anatomical elements that make up the described ensemble. Descriptions differ depending on who performs them. In some cases, the description of an individual by the eyewitness may be incomplete or even erroneous because of objective or subjective circumstances that prevent good perception. As a person can be distinguished from another, in a Forensic Sciences and yet identified way, it is necessary to describe his anatomical characteristics according to scientific methods, using appropriate terminology and precise criteria for dimensioning. In this sense, the identification is carried out by means of specialized methods and techniques in the framework of criminal prosecution activities, carried out according to tactical rules specific to the hearing of the witnesses or victims of the offense.

KEYWORDS: color, figure, forensic identification, signs, spoken portrait

Introduction

The foundation of the portrait was established in the XV Century by Leonardo da Vinci, who systematized the organs of the human body, appreciating them to be diverse: straight, concave, convex. It indicates that the technique of describing the portrait is the way to retain and reproduce the profile of a human figure after being seen once (Lucard 1932, 119). Every person has a certain, objective, invariable individuality in its essence and easily identifiable. It must be borne in mind that man is constantly and continuously evolving his particular features. Body features can also allow for changes that are largely conditioned by man's aspiration, such as the port of beard, mustache, the development of corporeality, the change in hair color, etc. Diseases or trauma suffered by the human body, certain surgical interventions may give rise to changes that are distinctive signs of that person. And age gives rise to changes that relate to the dimensions of certain organs or parts of the body, except those that have a bone or cartilage structure. The identification of persons by the portrait method is based on the principles of forensic identification, which is based on the thesis of didactic materialism, according to which all the objects of the material world are identical by themselves, they are individual and their characteristics are not repeated (Engels 1966, 180).

In describing the signals of a person, a precise and unitary terminology must be used, in a logical sequence. The description of the signals is done from the front or from the frontal plane and from the profile or from the lateral plane. The features of the head and face hold the main place in the realization of the spoken portrait and will be completed with the description of the whole body and of the clothing (Buzatu 2013, 92).

Head description

In Forensic practice and theory, the main elements of the face are described according to their location, starting with those located in the upper area, continuing with the middle and the lower ones. The figure of a person is examined from profile or front and includes face areas, respectively:

- a. The frontal area, limited to the top of the hair insertion area and continuing to the root of the nose;
- b. The nasal area between the root of the nose and the base of the nose;
- c. The mouth area includes the face portion between the base of the nose and the chin tip.

Five areas, namely forehead, eyes, nose, mouth and chin, can be considered, but the description will not be limited to them. Each constituent element of the figure will be described separately with the characteristic or particular elements, respectively:

The hair

Hair on the head is described by: color, nature, thread direction, insertion and hair loss. The color of the hair is marked according to the variants of shades: black-blue, black, dark brown, light brown, blond-red, blonde-gold, gray blond, platinum, gray and white.

Depending on the nature of the hair, it is classified as: thick and slim hair, the right hair - medium as thread thickness, curly hair, slick hair, curly hair. The hair port is determined by the type of combing presented in various shapes: right-hand, left-hand, middle-right, short-cut, full-grained, completely knotless. The hairline direction depends on its length. As direction, the thread can be oriented straight, forward, backward, left or right. Hair density is appreciated as dense, medium, rare, and intermediate. The insertion of hair on a person's forehead can be: straight, convex or concave. Cheeks can be appreciated as: large, appropriate or small, indicating their frontal, parietal or occipital position. Also, the data on how to cut the hair in front of the ears, indicating whether or not they are preferred, what is the size and form of their completion.

Forehead

Forehead can be viewed both from the front and the profile, insisting on the height, width, contour, inclination and peculiarities. The height of the forehead is appreciated as tripartite: high, medium or small relative to the distance between the hair and the root of the nose. The middle form is considered to be the normal height of the forehead.

As regards the width of the forehead, the description is made after a tripartite classification: narrow, medium or wide, after the distance between the two temples. Leaning of the forehead is established by reporting the real inclination to an imaginary vertical plane that runs through the base and root of the nose. Depending on this imaginary plane, the forehead is considered to be vertical, bulging, prominent, oblique, or fugitive. To consider that the forehead position is normal, it should be slightly inclined. Among the peculiarities we can mention in the forehead description: the protrusion of the arches, the frontal sinus, the frontal bosses and the curved profile.

Arcades can be large, medium or large. Their size varies with the angle of inclination of the bone protrusion located above the nose, on the center of the forehead, and the frontal bones that also constitute bone protrusions are located in the lateral sides of the forehead.

They can be remarked as peculiarities: excessive lifting, ridding the forehead, deep grooves in the depth of it. As the constituent elements of the forehead are the arches and can be appreciated according to the size: large, medium, small and are reported by the degree of inclination of forehead.

Eyebrows

They are hairstyles placed above the eyes and are appreciated by their length, thickness, thickness, arc, direction, or position occupied by eyeball or color. In some cases, the eyebrows may be missing altogether, or they may be made up of a few splinters or may also be cosmetically tattooed. By length, the eyebrows can be long, medium or short, as well as thin, well-suited, very often quite stiff. Depending on the arc, they may be straight, arched upwards or downwards, serpentine, angular, and after the direction they are straight, oblique up or down. The distance between them can be: merged, close or distant. The hair color of the person concerned is taken into account when describing the color of the eyebrows, with the indication that capillary hair discolours faster. As peculiarities, the eyebrows may be lowered, overburdened, or exhibiting specific forms due to scars, depilation, or pins.

The eyes

They represent the organs of sight and are located in the orbital cavity at the level of the base. In the composition of the eyeball, the retina, a photoreceptor formation, elements of it that assure the projection of the light on the retina. The ocular bulb consists of three membranes: sclerotic, retina, choroid, cornea, aqueous humor, lens and glassy humor. From the visible parts we mention the pupil, iris and sclerotica or the white of the eyes. The eyelids have a protective role and therefore their eyes

are protected by them. The eyelids close the base of the orbit, delineate the palpal crack that opens during the operation of the visual apparatus and closes during sleep.

In making the portrait, the eyes are presented in shape, position, color, interocular space, eyelid peculiarities, genes, depth in orbit (Stancu 2010,174). Each individual has an iris characteristic pigmentation that cannot be easily recalled or appreciated, because in some opinions it is influenced by light. According to other opinions, this pigmentation remains stable in adults (Voinea 1999,10).

According to the orifice, the eyes can be described as righteous, with external or inner commands raised or lowered, by size they can be large, medium or small. Orbital placement is appreciated from the profile, so the eyes can be clogged in orbits, prominent or normal.

The iris, the colored strip around the pupil, is the one that defines the color of the eyes. The most common eye colors are: black, brown, blue, gray, green, and in some cases may be discolored. Among the peculiarities that are recorded as particular signs we can remember his eyes, the missing eye, the different color of the two eyes, the presence of cataracts, the opacity of the cornea, the total lack of color.

Also interested in eyelids, genes, eye orbits or interocular space. The eyelids are presented in length, breadth, description, and whether they are large, medium or small. The genes are described by orientation, length or length and can be: Straight, oriented up or down; long, suitable or short; frequent or rare. Orbits of eyes are valued in terms of their height and depth: high or low, hollow or full. Interaction space is appreciated according to the distance between the two eyes and may be small, very small, appropriate, large or very large.

Nose

It is the olfactory organ, with an important role in sketching human physiognomy as a dominant element in the composition of the face and which can be observed and retained after the size of the nasal pyramid after the contour line or base.

The first segment of the respiratory apparatus is formed by the nose, in the form of a downward-facing pyramid, somewhat limited by the cross-section of the eyebrows, and at the bottom of the upper lip region.

There are some exceptions that differ in some breeds, namely: the right nose is specific to the Greeks, the Romanian aquilla, the African Americans have a wider nose in the lower part of the nose, and the Europeans have a light nose. The nose is examined both from the front and the profile. The elements that play an important role in making the portrait are: the root of the nose, the contour line, the base of the nose, the height and width, the protrusion of the nasal pyramid and the possible particularities. Observation should be related to the position it has been assessed (Voinea 1999, 10).

The root of the nose represents the hollow between the eye and eyebrow arches, and is appreciated in terms of depth; according to this principle they meet: the root, the middle root or the small root. According to the frontal observation, the root of the nose may be wide, suitable or narrow. The nose of the nose begins from the deepest part of the nose root and ends at its base. It is generally seen from the profile and can take various forms such as rectilinear, aquiline, corrugated, concave, etc.

The base of the nose is described both in the aspect of the direction and the width of the nose, the latter being the width of the nose. The imaginary line that starts from the point of connection of the nostril with the human figure to the tip of the nose determines the direction of the base of the nose. The direction can be seen from the profile and can be horizontal, raised or lowered.

The height and width of the nose is observed and appreciated, looking individually in the profile, being also replicated by the vertical line joining the root of the nose with the base of the nose base with the naso-labial groove. Under the height, it may be large, medium or small, and broad, medium or narrow width.

The nostrils' conformity is noted with certain characteristics, without the use of gradations of size, appreciating them in the particularities of: glued, dilated, turned, tightened, raised or flattened on one side. The tip of the nose is noted as a peculiarity without the use of gradations such as: thin, thick, bilobed, deviated to the right, diverted to the left, etc.

The color of the nose generally has the same hue with the rest of the face, but not in all cases. Sometimes the color of the nose may be different, especially at the tip of the nose, which may appear under a red, red-brown, violet shade, indicating some skin diseases, a state of debilitating or even excessive drinking.

Among the peculiarities are scars, warts, excessive pore expansion, congenital or accidental malformations.

The mouth area

It includes the lower part of the face, from the subchannel groove to the top of the chin, including the mouth, lips, teeth and chin and forms the lower third of the human figure (Dragomir, Nițu and Boalbeș 2008, 243).

The mouth is examined from the front and from the profile, both as a general aspect and as a peculiarity. As a general aspect, the size and orientation of the corners are described. The size of the mouth is appreciated by three gradations such as: small, medium, large but there may also be intermediate variations between them. The mouths of the mouth and the comics can be lifted up, very high, horizontal or appropriate, lowered or very lowered. They may also experience a unilateral deviation to the right or to the left following a habit, congenital illness or malformation.

Lips malformations, considered as peculiarities, are: rabbit lip, scarring, elevation of the median lower lip, lower lip hanging. The teeth are positioned in the alveolar edge of the two maxillaries and are grouped as follows: 8 incisors, 4 canines, 8 premolars and 12 molars. They can be described in terms of size, distance, position, color, degree of wear and can be: long, outward, distant, missing, fake, dressed.

In general, the incisors are described, namely their shape, the distance between them, if they are out, the way the root is dressed by the gum, because they are discovered and can be sensed during speech or laughter. A number of abnormalities can be observed, some of them congenital: incisors discovered, distant, welded, inclined outward or inward, incisive; but also acquired abnormalities such as the absence of one or more incisors, horizontal fracture, wear, caries.

Chin

The beard is the lowest part of the human figure, it continues the face and gives it the form that characterizes it. It can be examined both from the front and from the profile of the inclination, height, width and its peculiarities. From the profile we can see a slanting or receding, vertical, preeminent chin. As peculiarities, we can remember the bilobate, elongated, double, prominent chub with chub (Ciopraga, Iacobuță 2001, 196).

Beard and mustaches are hair accessories located in the mouth, described in terms of shape, size, position or color. The beard is considered large when it encompasses the whole face, its hair being long, small or barby when the hair is short on the entire face. It may also appear as a beak, a bundle of yarn, located at the bottom of the chin. By shape, the beard may be a sailor, a collar, a beard full, etc. Musts can be large with corners raised or lowered, cut small on the lip, or small after the width of the nose, arched in the shape of the swallowtail, etc.

Ear

It is appreciated as one of the most informative organs of the face. It is of particular importance because of its position on the contour of the head, but also its shape, size or other morphological elements (Doroș 1996, 205). It is recorded that the ear has a double character, i.e. it is immutable in form, from birth to death and variable, in other words, two similar ears do not meet (Cârjan, and Chipier 2009, 187).

Head position is parallel to the cranial bone, but in some people the ears may be located at the top or bottom.

The outer ear pavilion consists of a set of cartilages, namely five ridges and three depressions. The characteristic elements are: helix, antihelix, tragus, antitragus, lobe or ear, conca or auditory aperture, digital depression and internal depression. They present various varieties of shape, position or proportions as will be briefly presented:

The helix, the ridge that surrounds the ear pavilion from the front to the rear; is composed of four parts: original, anterior, superior, inferior; may be large, medium or small.

Antihelix, the cartilage cartilage located inside the ear, parallel to the upper and posterior helix; may be complete, apparently only in the upper area or absent.

Tragus, protrusion from cartilage tissue positioned under the original helix that partially covers the auditory aperture; the volume is rated as high, medium or small; can be sharp, bifurcated or prominent.

Antitragus, prominence of the cartilage located in the lower part of the ear shell and can be described as: concave, convex, bulging, straight.

The lob or ear, the fleshy lower part of the ear pavilion, which has various shapes, sizes, and with respect to the contour of the free part of the lobe can be presented as square, scattered, angular, in the echery, etc.

Conca, the depression formed in the mouth of the auditory aperture, which is presented as a funnel and is appreciated being related to the other elements of the ear pavilion.

The digital depression is located behind the helix before and under the top helix.

The internal depression is located between the posterior upper helix and the earlobe's antihelix with an elongated shape (Doros 1996, 205).

As peculiarities can be mentioned the bifurcated tragus, the sharp ears in the upper part, the notched edge, the ears very close to the head etc.

Wrinkles are leather creases that can be caused by either aging or expression. They are described by depth, shape, number, and the area of the face where they are positioned. Wrinkles can be corrected through surgical procedures, women are most often used in such procedures, and this should be mentioned if it is noticeable (Popa 2011, 25).

Skin color or chromaticity peculiarities vary by race. The color varies from white to black and is essential for making the portrait spoken. It should be noted that some people will change the color of their skin by exposure to the sun, its discoloration, the use of make-up or make-up, aspect to be considered.

Conclusions

When a person's spoken portrait is drawn, the characterization of the signs will be made according to size, shape, position, and some and color.

Size is shown by comparison with the size of other parts of the body and will be noted with small, mediocre and great; when the detail is particularly small or very large it will be marked with very little or very large.

The shape is reproduced by the linear outer contour of the organ to be presented to fit into one of the geometric figures that is similar: round, oval, diamond, triangle, rectangle.

The color will be recorded for details that have this attribute, such as the skin, hair, eyes or other organs or parts of organs showing a particular coloring to the rest of the skin.

The position of a human body detail will be judged relative to the horizontal or vertical plane or neighboring areas, the notation being horizontal, vertical or oblique. When identifying a person's signals, certain factors that affect the accuracy of their observation and retention must be taken into account. The main factors responsible for this influence are the following: the distance from which it is viewed, the place where the person is located, the time when the observation is performed and the factors that may influence: day, night, atmospheric conditions, visibility, duration of observation, as well as its clothing, the ability to perceive and the appreciation of the observer.

The primordial assimilation of the principles of the portrait spoken by the police and their skillful application allow a visible and coherent description of the anatomical and functional signs of the different people.

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